

Composition and antimicrobial activity study on essential oil from the aerial parts of Chinese licorice (*Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch.)

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Abstract : *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch. has been used in Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) as one of the most important crude drug for thousands of years. By steam distillation, the essential oil from the aerial parts of licorice (*Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch.) was obtained and analyzed by GC-MS. 28 components representing 74.39% of the total oil content were identified for the first time in this species. The main compounds in the oil were β -cadinene (12.28%), β -caryophyllene (10.04%), γ -cadinene (9.49%), phytol (8.43%), α -cadinene (4.43%), caryophyllene oxide (3.65%) and α -gurjunene (3.48%). The antimicrobial activity of the oil was evaluated by investigation of MIC and MBC.

Keywords : *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch., essential oil, GC/MS, steam distillation, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Glycyrrhiza uralensis Fisch., family Leguminosae, a most important ingredient of Chinese traditional medicine used from ancient times, was found in Chinese traditional prescriptions at the rate of 60%¹. Its roots and stolons have long been employed as one of the most important crude drug as well as flavoring and sweetening agents². The constituents and activities of the crude material have been studied by many investigators³⁻⁶. Among about 200 chemical constituents, triterpenoids and flavonoids have been demonstrated the major ingredients and have several important pharmacological activities⁷. The traditional pharmacological effects of licorice as a dietary supplement for stomach ulcers, bronchitis, and sore throat, as well as infections caused by viruses, such as hepatitis, including anti-viral, anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-ulcer, anti-cancer and anti-HIV have been well verified^{1,8-10}.

Numerous bioactive compounds are present in licorice. Nevertheless, essential oil's composition and its biological activities have never been reported from aerial parts of this species according to our knowledge. In this study, we utilized steam distillation for extraction of the

essential oil. Its components was analysed by GC-MS and its antibacterial activity was studied by the broth microdilution method bioassay. This provides evidence for deeper exploitation and utilization of licorice resources.

Results and discussion

Gas chromatography/mass spectrometry analysis :

The constituents were well separated on the DB-5MS column at our experiment condition. The complete list of the identified compounds appears in Table 1 in order of their elution on DB-5MS column. 28 components were characterized, which represented 74.39% of the total peak area.

Essential oils are very important components of traditional herbal medicines, and have many biological activities, possibly related to their functions in plants^{11,12}. The major components were identified by comparison of their mass spectral data with the NIST library and literature data¹³⁻¹⁵. The principal identified components were terpenes and alcohols.

The essential oil is formed of a high number of sesquiterpenes and monoterpenes, representing more than 50% of the total oil. The principal identified components

Table 1. Essential oil constituents from the aerial parts of *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch.

No.	R.T. (min)	Compds.	<i>m/z</i>	Similarity	%	Identified by
1	5.04	3-Carene	136	883	0.6	MS
2	5.86	β -Pinene	136	819	1.25	R, MS
3	7.66	2-Carene	136	788	0.30	MS
4	24.65	α -Cubebene	204	852	0.32	MS
5	26.89	Ylangene	204	712	0.15	MS
6	27.60	Copaene	204	904	2.02	MS
7	31.16	(-)- α -Gurjunene	204	904	3.48	R, MS
8	32.28	α -Bergamotene	204	820	0.96	MS
9	32.63	β -Caryophyllene	204	884	10.04	R, MS
10	37.25	α -Caryophyllene	204	890	1.67	MS
11	37.78	Alloaromadendrene	204	891	1.52	MS
12	38.11	Isocaryophyllene	204	854	1.06	MS
13	41.23	β -Himachalene	204	836	1.81	MS
14	43.10	Eremophilene	204	880	1.16	MS
15	43.98	(-)- α -Cadinene	204	912	4.43	MS
16	45.94	γ -Cadinene	204	703	9.49	MS
17	47.12	β -Cadinene	204	889	12.28	R, MS
18	56.42	Caryophyllene oxide	220	787	3.65	MS
19	57.26	Viridiflorol	222	727	0.39	MS
20	60.38	Ledol	222	756	1.80	MS
21	70.26	Torreyol	222	684	1.08	MS
22	109.84	Perhydrofarnesyl acetone	268	766	1.95	MS
23	117.46	9,17-Octadecadienal,(z)-	264	850	0.88	MS
24	118.27	Linolenyl alcohol	264	825	2.36	MS
25	119.24	13-Octadecenal,(z)-	266	781	0.21	MS
26	122.18	Crocetane	296	687	0.87	MS
27	160.62	Phytol	296	826	8.43	R, MS
28	172.67	Octadecyl acetate	312	741	0.23	MS
	Total				74.39	

R.T. : Retention time; R : Reference substance (purity >90%); MS : Mass spectra; % : Calculated from TIC data.

in this fraction were β -cadinene (12.28%), β -caryophyllene (10.04%), γ -cadinene (9.49%), α -cadinene (4.43%) and α -gurjunene (3.48%). Alcohols were present in the essential oil in relatively low amounts, representing more than 10% of the total oil, which were mainly phytol (8.43%), linolenyl alcohol (2.36%), cyclododecanol (2.18%) and ledol (1.8%). In addition to the compounds cited above, there were small quantities of terpene derivatives and aromatic esters. Most of the components are different from the seed essential oil of this species. Constituents of essential oil from aerial parts contains more active components compared with that from the seeds.

Determination of MIC and MBC :

The antibacterial activity of essential oil from aerial parts of *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch. has been evaluated for the first time and shown in Table 2. From the data, we can see that *Listeria monocytogenes* is sensitive to this essential oil with MIC values of 0.25 to 0.5%. The antibacterial effect in general can be evaluated as moderate because most of the MICs are higher than 0.5%. The concentration of the essential oil was due to the small sample volume to reach definite MIC values of other bacterial. Further studies need to be done to give the MIC values.

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of essential oil from aerial parts of *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch. against gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria

Bacterial strain	MIC %	MBC %
	(v/v)	(v/v)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 11229	>0.5	>0.5
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ATCC 10031	>0.5	>0.5
<i>Shigella flexneri</i> ATCC 29903	>0.5	>0.5
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i> ATCC 14153	>0.5	>0.5
<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i> ATCC 13048	>0.5	>0.5
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> ATCC 15442	>0.5	>0.5
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ATCC 15313	0.25-0.5	0.5->0.5
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 6538	>0.5	>0.5
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> NCTC 10442	0.5->0.5	>0.5
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> ATCC 49134	>0.5	>0.5
<i>Staphylococcus saprophyticus</i> ATCC 15305	0.5->0.5	>0.5
<i>Enterococcus faecium</i> ATCC 11229	>0.5	>0.5

It is very difficult to attribute the antimicrobial effect of a total essential oil to one or a few active principles, because an essential oil always contains a mixture of different chemical compounds. In addition to the major compounds, also minor compounds are making a significant contribution to the oil's activity. It's still not clear that which compound or which combinations of compounds are responsible for the antimicrobial activity against the used bacteria in this licorice species.

Experimental

Plant material :

Fresh stem and leaves about 10 cm above the ground of three-year old *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch. were collected in Xia Tian licorice base of Heilongjiang Province in China in August 2003 and then cut into 2 ~ 5 cm pieces. It was identified by Professon S. Q. Nie and a voucher specimen has been deposited at the Key Laboratory of Forest Plant Ecology, Northeast Forestry University.

Oil preparation :

The essential oil was obtained by water steam distillation for 3 h. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used to absorb little water that the essential oil contained and then stored at -20 °C until analyzed.

Gas chromatography/mass spectrometry analysis :

Analyse of the oil sample was run on a VG platform II GC-MS system equipped with a DB-5MS capillary column (30 × 0.25 mm i.d.; film thickness 0.25 µm). The

oven temperature was programmed from 60 to 100 °C at 8 °C/min, then to 180 °C at 0.7 °C/min and this temperature was held for 5 min and then to 250 °C at 6 °C/min, which was held for 2 min. Source and FID detector temperatures were 180 °C and 250 °C respectively. Carrier gas was helium (99.999%) at a flow rate of 1 ml/min and with a solvent delay time of 3 min. The ionization of the sample components was performed in the EI mode (70 eV). Mass range was from *m/z* 50 to 500. Compounds were identified by reference substance and comparing their mass information with NIST database. Peak areas were measured by electronic integration. The percentage of the oil components was computed from the GC peak areas without any correction for the relative response factors.

Test microorganisms :

All bacteria used for susceptibility testing were test strains derived from Type Culture Collections (ATCC, USA; NCTC, UK; DSM, Germany) and from blood culture samples (BC) isolated in the routine laboratory of the Institute of Hygiene, University Hospital Heidelberg.

Microbial cultures :

Bacteria were incubated overnight in Iso-Sensitest Broth (Oxoid) at 37 °C. After 20 ± 2 h the inocula were adjusted to approximately 5 × 10⁵ colony forming units (CFU) per ml. The colony number was verified by the spiral plater counting method.

Each well of the plate was filled with 100 µl test or control solution and 100 µl bacterial inoculum. The plates were inoculated at 37 °C for 20 ± 2 h.

MIC and MBC :

The antibacterial activity of essential oils was determined by evaluating their minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) and minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBCs) against a panel of bacterial strains, using a modified broth microdilution method according to the German DIN regulation 58940-7. The MIC is defined as the lowest concentration of the antibacterial agent that inhibits visible growth of bacteria, i.e. a turbidity or precipitation of bacteria at the bottom of the wells. The MBC was determined by seeding 10 µl from each well on an agar plate which was then incubated for further 24 h at 37 °C. The MBC is defined as the lowest concentration without colony growth. Because the test sample was instable emulsions, the wells of the microtiter plate showed a turbidity

and precipitation even without bacterial growth, which impaired the correct reading of the MIC. This problem was solved by adding of 10 μ l of the redox reagent *p*-iodonitrotetrazolium-violet (0.5% in aqueous solution) to each well. The presence of growing bacteria turns the colorless salt to the red formazan. The MIC could be read as the lowest concentration of the test substance which stayed colorless after addition of the dye.

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